

TOOLPATH STRATEGY & GENERATION FOR ROBOTIC FIBRE PLACEMENT ON CURVED SURFACES

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RESEARCH SUMMARY

An approach to use RFP (Robotic fibre placement) technology to fabricate composites with curvatures, through path planning and placement control of continuous fibres was conducted. Particularly, research and development of a simple tool for trajectory generation on freeform curved surfaces is attempted. Toolpath and its optimization for fibre layup on curved surfaces was implemented. The main aim of the study was to develop a simple algorithm to generate toolpaths for layup of pre-impregnated unidirectional towpregs (prepregs slit into narrow tows) on curved moulds. The various stages of the placement process or computational design methodology used in this approach are described, beginning with digital path planning and modelling, followed by programming and simulation, and concluding with tool path generation, and physical part fabrication. The research demonstrates how composites having similar curved contours can be processed with AFP

FIBRE PLACEMENT HEAD (FPH) & CONTROL SYSTEM

FIBRE PLACEMENT HEAD – OPERATION FLOWCHART

TOOLPATH GENERATION – PROCESS FLOWCHART

PATH GENERATION ALGORITHM

Points of Interest (Targets, T):

- Start & End points of each course.
- Points to command motion paths.
- Points to command tow cut at desired locations (min 100mm).
- Offset points to command motion between intermediate points (Start, End).
- Points to improve resolution at corners/ negative features.

Path design flow:

- Path design flow representation for 0 degree layup is shown in the sequence of figures (a) to (f).

ROBOTIC FIBRE PLACEMENT – SIMULATION

Before the actual placement process, the sequence of movements that iterate the layup process is simulated and thoroughly checked for abnormalities. This is done in a virtual environment to verify that there are no unexpected maneuvers, collisions or incorrect tool orientations/positions present, for a safer execution. The figures show a few of frames from the simulated layup process for one layer.

ROBOTIC FIBRE PLACEMENT – FABRICATION

The above figures show the actual fiber placement process employed. Good adhesion of the first layer onto the test surface was achieved through optimum pressure control of the compaction roller. Perfect adhesion of the following layers was also achieved, thanks to the repeated compaction of tows. Validation of the placement quality: Gaps (0mm -2mm) and overlaps between courses or tows in the different plies or layers were observed.

APPLICATIONS & OUTLOOK

The projection algorithm or approach used in this study finds its application in the manufacturing of aircraft wings, wind turbines, etc. and components with moderately complex curved features. Ongoing research includes the toolpath planning for tubular parts using an external rotary axis.

Future Work: Study of the effects and influence of different layup speeds on the placement process as well as on the quality of layup observed. Use the data obtained to identify defects and implement fixes optimizing the existing approach or through re-designed placement paths/alternate algorithms.